

Synthesis and Pharmacological Screening of New 1-(Substituted-aminomethyl)-2-oxo-3-[4-phenyl-5-(4-substituted/unsubstituted-phenoxyphenylazo)-2-thiazolyl]iminoindoles

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VARIOUS indoles are known to possess biological activities¹. In the present work 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole was treated with diazonium chloride in presence of sodium acetate and ethanol to give 2-amino-4-phenyl-5-(4-substituted/unsubstituted-phenoxyphenylazo)thiazoles (2a, b). Reaction of 2a, b with isatin in ethanol with glacial acetic acid yielded 2-oxo-3-[4-phenyl-5-(4-substituted/unsubstituted-phenoxyphenylazo)-2-thiazolyl]imino-indoles (3a, b), which underwent Mannich reaction in presence of formaldehyde and different secondary amines to afford the title compounds (4a-h).

Experimental

M.ps. were taken in a sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. The purity of compounds was checked on silica gel G plates. Ir spectra were taken on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer.

2-Amino-4-phenylthiazole (1): It was prepared by the reported method².

2-Amino-4-phenyl-5-(4-substituted/unsubstituted-phenoxyphenylazo)thiazoles (2a, b): The compounds were prepared by the reported method³. Sodium nitrite (0.02 mol) dissolved in water (25 ml) was gradually added to a well-cooled solution of an appropriate amine in 3*N* HCl (2.5 ml). The diazonium salt solution was filtered into a cooled suspension of the thiazole (1) and sodium acetate (5 g) in ethanol (50 ml). After 2 h the resulting solid was washed several times with water and recrystallised from DMF-ethanol mixture (1 : 1): ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 620–1 610 (C=N), 1 580–1 575 (N=N) and 1 200 cm^{-1} (Ar-O-Ar).

2-Oxo-3-[4-phenyl-5-(4-substituted/unsubstituted-phenoxyphenylazo)-2-thiazolyl]imino-indoles (3a, b): A mixture of equimolar quantities of isatin and 2a/b in ethanol containing glacial acetic acid (2–3 drops) was refluxed on a water-bath for 4 h. The solid which separated on cooling, was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol: ν_{\max} 3 440 (NH), 1 690 (C=O), 1 590–1 575 (N=N) and 2 920–2 940 cm^{-1} (C–H); elemental analyses were found to be within range.

1-(Substituted/unsubstituted-aminomethyl)-2-oxo-3-[4-phenyl-5-(4-substituted-phenoxyphenylazo)-2-thiazolyl]imino-indoles (4a-h): A suspension of the

Scheme 1

appropriate indole (3a/b; 0.005 mol) in methanol (10 ml) was warmed on a water-bath and to it 37% formalin (1 ml) and an appropriate amine (0.005 mol) were added with vigorous stirring.

The reaction mixture was then allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. The resulting solid was washed with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and recrystallised from ethyl acetate/chloroform-petroleum ether (Table 1): ν_{\max} 3 440 (NH), 1690 (C=O), 1 590–1 575 (N=N) and 2 920–2 940 cm^{-1} (CH); $4a \delta$ (CDCl_3) 6.67–7.52 (22H, m), 2.44–2.66 (8H, t, N-CH_2), and 5.02 (2H, s).

Biological screening:

All compounds (4a–h) were screened for toxicity and gross CNS effects in mice. The compounds were administered intraperitoneally to groups of 4 albino mice of either sex (18–22 g) in graded doses and observed over a period of 24 h. ALD_{50} and 1/5th of ALD_{50} values were calculated*. Behavioural changes in spontaneous motor activity (SMA) and reactivities to sound and touch were observed.

All the compounds (4a–h) were screened for cardiovascular activity in cat (3–4 kg) of either sex (at doses 1 and 5 mg/kg i.v.). anaesthetised with sodium pentobarbital (35 mg/kg ip). The right common carotid artery was cannulated and blood pressure was recorded. Respiration was recorded through a Marey's tambour after cannulating the trachea. The contraction of nictitating membrane was recorded by stimulating the preganglionic cervical sympathetic nerve through bipolar electrode. Square wave pulses (0.1 Hz of 0.5 ms duration, 2–5 V for 5s) were delivered from a Grass model S_4 stimulator. The contractions were recorded. All test substances and reference standards, acetylcholine chloride (0.1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$), adrenaline hydrochloride (1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) histamine acid phosphate (0.1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) and isoprenaline sulphate (1–2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) were administered through an indwelling polythene cannula in right femoral vein followed by 1 ml of normal saline.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS (4a–b)*

Compd. no.	$\begin{array}{c} \text{R}^1 \\ \\ -\text{N} \\ \\ \text{R}^2 \end{array}$		Mol. formula	m.p. °C
	R=Cl			
4a	N-Phenyl piperazino		$\text{C}_{40}\text{H}_{33}\text{N}_7\text{SClO}_2$	120
4b	Morpholino		$\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{27}\text{N}_6\text{SClO}_2$	117
4c	N-Ethyl		$\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{29}\text{N}_6\text{SClO}_2$	102
	R=H			
4d	Morpholino		$\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{23}\text{N}_6\text{SO}_2$	104
4e	N-Ethyl		$\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{25}\text{N}_6\text{SO}_2$	111
4f	N-Phenyl piperazino		$\text{C}_{40}\text{H}_{33}\text{N}_7\text{SO}_2$	116
4g	N-Methyl piperazino		$\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{SO}_2$	120
4h	N-Methyl anilino		$\text{C}_{37}\text{H}_{25}\text{N}_6\text{SO}_2$	112

* All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses; yield=60–85%.

The compounds were screened for anti-inflammatory activity following the reported method⁵ on albino rats of either sex (100–150 g). The animals were divided into groups of five. The control group received the vehicle p.o. The test compounds (100 mg/kg) were also administered orally. After 1 h, carrageenin (0.1 ml) solution (1%, w/v) was injected subcutaneously in the left hand paw. Volume of the injected limb was measured by volume differential meter immediately and 4 h after injection. The mean difference in oedema of the rat in the control group and drug treated groups was calculated and the percentage inhibition calculated. Phenylbutazone (30 mg/kg) was used as the standard.

Five compounds were screened against Ranikhet disease virus⁶ in the stationary culture of chorioallantoic membrane of chick embryo. Chorioallantoic membrane (CAM) of 10 days old chick embryo was taken and culture prepared according to the reported method of Babbar⁷.

Results and Discussion

All compounds (4a–h) screened for toxicity and CNS activity were found to be non-toxic having ALD_{50} values more than 1000 mg/kg. Compounds having R=Cl were found to be depressant in nature (4a–c), and those having R=H were found to be both stimulant (4f–h) as well as depressant (4d, e) in nature. Thus it may be concluded that presence of chloro group possibly increase the depressant activity.

CVS effect of all the compounds was transient, chloro substituted indoles were more active against CVS activity. Compounds 4a, b, e and h exhibited anti-inflammatory activity (14–22%), with 4a having maximum inhibition of 22%. Out of eight compounds (4a–c, f and g) screened for antiviral activity, compounds having R=H (4f, g) exhibited marked activity (20–40%).

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